

-Online teaching of university mathematics in multicultural South Africa: a community of practice perspective

Sudan Hansraj
Rituparno Goswami
Anesh Maharaj
Gareth Amery
Raushan Quadir
Keshlan Govinder

Oluwatosin Temitope Mewomo

School of Mathematics, Statistics and Computer Science, University of KwaZulu Natal, Durban, South Africa, 4041

ABSTRACT: The shift from traditional classroom teaching to the online modality, catalyzed by the SARS-Covid-19 pandemic, necessitated a forced transformation in pedagogy. In fact the entire didactical foundations of mathematics teaching were shaken at all levels. We analyze these effects qualitatively in a range of introductory, intermediate-level and senior level university mathematics courses. The sample consisted of mathematics students from the University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. The new content delivery approach is briefly considered and then assessment and evaluation implications are evaluated. It emerged that lecturers favoured a return to standard teaching for novice students, a hybrid form of presentation in the intermediate phase and a possible complete online delivery mode for mature students. The success of all of these approaches is contingent on ensuring the integrity of assessment processes. The ramifications of these proposals are also interrogated.

Keywords: University Mathematics Teaching; Online Teaching; Digital Classroom; Content Delivery Strategies; Assessment of Online Pedagogy,

Introduction

Theoretical Framework

Research Question

Methodology

First Level Teaching (first year)

Intermediate Level teaching (second year)

Final Level Teaching (3rd and 4th year: specialist courses)

Impact of online system on pass rates

Analysis and the way forward

Conclusions

Bibliography

1. Introduction

The covid-19 pandemic has revolutionised modalities of teaching in all disciplines of knowledge and at all levels of study globally [1]. Students had to be rapidly moved to the online learning platforms as severe lockdowns were implemented in many countries due to the spread of the covid-19 virus. Regular classroom based teaching with its normal social interactions had to be suspended until such time that it was safe to resume in-person learning. As a result students had to also learn new styles of self-learning to mitigate the

loss of teaching time due to the hard lockdowns. The University was best able to assimilate the new formats given its access to resources. A swift transformation to online or digital modes of teaching was forced upon the global teaching fraternity [2, 3]. It would be safe to say that some of the foundations of traditional education theory and practice have been irreversibly shaken. The learning theories espoused by eminent educationists require careful reconsideration as a new form of educating takes root. Admittedly, most learning theories were devised through investigations during the early stages of human development from birth to around the end of high school and very little behavioural research of adults such as are at a university, has been done. Nevertheless, well founded learning theories serve as a natural springboard to commence analysing educating at the adult level.

For example the Vygotsky [4] school of thought emphasises the fundamental value of social interaction in the development of cognition. The learner is viewed as a social constructivist and learns through problem solving but is heavily dependent on peers and more capable entities such as the teacher. But social interactions have been severely curtailed due to the prevailing covid-19 pandemic. Human interactions have proceeded minimalistically on a needs-basis during the pandemic. Hence the social environment is highly regulated and not prone to incidental learning as would be the case in regular day-to-day social interactions with class mates and teachers. However, Vygotsky did conjure the idea of a zone of proximal development wherein the learner firstly considers what he/ she can learn by themselves and then what can be learnt from others including technology. The latter has certainly leaped into relevance during the lockdown stages of the pandemic and its future in fundamental pedagogics merits deep reflection.

Differing from Vygotsky, Piaget [5] de-emphasises social interactions and perceives the learner as a cognitive constructivist following well defined development levels through principles such as equilibration, schema, adaptation, assimilation and accommodation. The basic idea is that the learner needs minimal intervention from the teacher and is capable of proceeding through the developmental levels with suitable support to explore their environment and attach meaning to it. In this regard pandemic conditions have demanded that learners adapt to reduced teacher support and instead the emphasis has shifted to self-learning. For example, online tools such as interactive tutorials, youtube videos, google and wiki pages, have been the hallmarks of modern pandemic learning styles. The ready availability of such mechanisms prompt a revised view of assessment practices. We discuss this later separately.

Indeed technology infused teaching of mathematics has always been debated in academic research circles albeit largely anecdotally [6, 7]. For example, Fishman et al. [8] enquired on the factors that governed the sustainability of technology-infused mathematics instruction. The technology itself has evolved in time from the use of calculators as a teaching and not principally a computational device, to the use of software packages to illustrate concepts and in recent times the technology has taken the entire classroom into the realm of virtual reality. Clearly, these are uncharted waters and unsurprisingly there exists a paucity of research in this area. In this paper, we consider perspectives from teaching practitioners themselves on the didactical adjustments that were made to

traditional teaching strategies and the impact the new mode of teaching had on student outcomes.

We also probe whether the modes of delivery have prospects of becoming permanent fixtures in the teaching of certain types of courses. Naturally, the consequences for the university as a project itself are manifold. By exploiting synergies amongst academic staff, the existing body of academics can be managed differently allowing for smaller teaching class units at the introductory levels and at the senior level allowing for the introduction of new mathematical topics which were previously suppressed due to resource constraints. At another level, if online teaching persists in senior classes at least, an impact on the physical infrastructure demands will be significant. In fact questions on the existence of the traditional university as an entity itself arise. The emergence of super-universities subsuming localised sites could be a reality. In this eventuality the future of academic work begs interrogation as mass teaching strategies entrench themselves. These deeper questions, will not be examined in this article, however, we raise them to motivate the importance and long term ramifications of the insights contained herein.

Research into the use of technology in mathematics teaching is not novel. Kaput [9] and Waits and Demana [10] expressed the view that preparation of 'tomorrow's teachers' to use technology is one of the most important issues facing today's teacher education programs in the school system. A 2010 generic study in Malaysia by Nida et al [11] explored whether teachers considered a laptop as a beneficial tool in lesson preparation and presentation. Teachers agreed that the 'laptop' enhanced teaching however, the study did not actually give concrete examples of how they benefitted. Moreover, the 'laptop' could have merely been a tool to access the internet where the real substance of influential ideas reside. The National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) [12] in the USA maintains that technology tools do 'support both the learning of mathematical procedures and skills as well as the development of advanced mathematical proficiencies, such as problem solving, reasoning, and justifying' (e.g., [13 -18])). So the impact of technology tools is well founded, however, for the purposes of our work we consider the changed modes of teaching offered through technology especially in university level teaching of mathematics.

The sudden onset of the worldwide pandemic and hence lockdowns forced the worldwide tertiary education to be completely on the online platforms. This sudden transition on one hand gave rise to extreme confusion and helplessness both on the part of facilitators and the facilitated [19, 20], while on the other side this forced academics to be more innovative in their approach and develop new techniques of knowledge transfer that can be easily blended to the normal classroom education when the world order comes back to normal in future. These views appear to have been felt elsewhere in the world. For example a report from a South Korean university details how junior and senior staff members were impacted differently by online teaching modes [21]. A report from Norway [22] details the approaches used in Norway and the inability of lecturers to fully understand the challenges faced by students. The study involved interviews with staff members and also a number of students. In the research of Cabuquin [23] insights into the experiences with modular and online learning in mathematics during the COVID-19 pandemic are provided. Although the

study includes responses from junior and senior high school students, the implications may be relevant for new teaching practices at the tertiary level as well. Mathias and others [24], discuss methods for engaging students in mathematics learning, with a focus on collaborative teaching. While the article does not explicitly mention COVID-19, the shift towards online collaborative teaching methods may have relevance in the context of the pandemic. The study of Yin and Yang, [25] addresses the methods used in teaching advanced mathematics courses online. They interviewed 273 college students majoring in mathematics and explored some 21 main teaching methods. It should also be noted that a shift to online teaching did arise in South Africa during 2015 to 2017 during protests by local students in favour of 'decolonized' education. A thorough coverage of the situation is contained in [22].

2. Theoretical Framework

Significant research has shown the value of the TPACK framework by Mishra and Koehler [23, 24] in integrating technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge for effective technology-based math teaching. This approach became crucial during the 2021-2022 pandemic, accelerating the adoption of online teaching tools like Mathematica, Maple, and MathLab, and methods such as live Zoom sessions with electronic whiteboards. Assessments shifted to online quizzes and electronic submissions, supported by studies like Schmid et al. [25], Fahadi and Khan [26], and Shin et al. [27], demonstrating TPACK's effectiveness in university math instruction.

3. Research Question

Through empirical means, we wish to analyse qualitatively whether pandemic-style teaching has a future in regular teaching approaches at the level of university mathematics. We have traced the epistemological directions of standard classroom teaching, acknowledged that technological interventions in mathematics teaching have been around for a while, but we probe whether online teaching can have a permanent place in university education principally in mathematics. We believe Mathematics as a discipline is well suited for this experiment given that it has minimal appeals to outside sources such as fieldwork and practicals.

4. Methodology

The study used a qualitative approach, with lecturers at the University of KwaZulu-Natal discussing online teaching via Zoom and Moodle, and their experiences assessing student performance. The outcomes, reflective in nature, did not involve extensive data collection, mirroring Trenholm and Peschke's [29] study comparing face-to-face and online teaching. Ethical clearance was deemed unnecessary as no direct student interactions occurred.

Significant research by Tallent-Runnels et al [30] and others explored online teaching dynamics, though not specifically in mathematics. Mishra et al [31] investigated online learning perceptions at an Indian university, and Tam and El-Azar [32] predicted

increasing educational innovations and digital inclusivity post-pandemic. Zayapragassarazan [33] advocated for flexible, learner-centered methods during this period.

This article classifies its analysis by student levels in mathematics: introductory specialist courses, basic professional courses, intermediate courses, and advanced courses, reflecting different mathematical content and online teaching adaptations at each level.

5. First Level teaching (First year)

We commence by considering reports from lecturers teaching very large classes of professionally oriented mathematics students in the first year. While the profile of this cohort differs significantly from cohorts specializing in mathematics, the basic approach and insights gained are applicable generically. Additionally, it may be noted that these courses feature applications of mathematics to the work of life scientists, engineers and management students and there is a de-emphasis of rigorous proof techniques and abstraction.

Mathematics for the management sciences

Content Delivery (CK, TK)

The Quantitative Management course focused on mathematical modeling, addressing systems of linear equations, linear programming, finance mathematics, and calculus applications (CK). It was structured with a detailed weekly schedule that included recorded write-on lectures (CK, TK), live tutorials, and online quizzes (PK, TK). All lecture materials were made available in advance to help students prepare effectively. The course format was well-received by students, who appreciated the ability to replay parts of the lectures and the transparency of the module delivery.

Assessment and Evaluation (PK, TK)

Assessments continued using the multiple-choice format, suitable for the large class sizes and comparable to previous non-pandemic years. The shift to online brought automation to the assessment process, increasing its challenge level (PK, TK). Concerns regarding the integrity of online assessments emerged, particularly the potential for student collusion via social media. Plans to improve assessment integrity include investing in anti-cheating software and considering the use of on-campus Local Area Networks for controlled, invigilated testing environments (PK, TK).

Mathematics for the life sciences

Content Delivery (CK, TK)

The course, delivered to approximately a thousand students, focused on calculus techniques relevant to professional disciplines like biomedical sciences and optometry (CK).

Initially, students faced challenges such as lack of suitable devices and poor internet connectivity, particularly in rural areas. Despite early apprehensions, the university helped students acquire necessary technology, allowing the program to proceed. Content delivery began with uploading static lecture notes to Moodle (PK, TK), progressing to adding voice-overs, and eventually transitioning to full video lectures via Zoom (TK). To enhance interaction and reduce isolation, a large number of teaching assistants were engaged for tutorial support, and a WhatsApp group was established for student and tutor communication (TK).

Assessment and Evaluation (PK, TK)

The evaluation strategy incorporated both formative and summative assessments. The transition to online assessments initially faced technical and cheating challenges, exacerbated by occasional electricity issues in South Africa. Despite these setbacks, improvements were made in evaluation techniques, and over time students adapted to the new teaching and learning environment, managing pandemic-related stresses more effectively.

Mathematics for engineers

Content Delivery (CK, TK)

This course was taken by students training to become professional engineers. The class size was large – around 700 and there were three teaching class units. The module was taught using Zoom by following the official university timetable for lectures and tutorials (PK). The lecture notes were written using a teaching tablet, saved in PDF format and projected to the students with detailed explanations during each lecture via Zoom (TK). Each lecture was recorded and the audio/ video uploaded on Moodle immediately after each lecture. Students downloaded these recordings and had the opportunity of going through the notes after the lecture time as many times as possible. They also had the opportunity of consultation with the lecturer on areas of concerns that they needed more clarification, information and explanation.

Assessment and Evaluation (PK and TK)

Assessments (Tests and Assignments) were done online using the Assignment Menu on Moodle with the strict instructions that late submissions would not be accepted. These instructions were intended to protect the integrity of the assessments. The major challenge of this method of assessment was to guarantee the integrity of the assessments as there is no software or gadget to authenticate the identity of those writing these assessments. The issue with supervision seems to be resolved to some extent as questions that are more or less like open books type were given to students. Both quizzes and essay type questions were used for assessments.

6. Intermediate Level Teaching (Second year)

We now consider the pandemic teaching experience at the second year level where students have better acclimatized at university and have become more familiar with the university's technology systems. For example, the Moodle system has been in use for over a decade as a content management system, even though most lecturing staff would have exploited only basic properties of the platform.

Discrete Mathematics with Applications

Content Delivery (CK, PK, TK)

The second-year course covered topics like set theory, number theory, and cryptology (CK). Material including notes and tutorials was uploaded onto Moodle. Pre-recorded lectures and tutorial videos were prepared in advance using OBS and uploaded for student access. Recap sessions and Q&A were held during the usual class times via Zoom and Big Blue Button, facilitating interactive learning (PK, TK).

Assessment and Evaluation (PK, TK)

Assessments were conducted entirely online using MCQs designed with up to 12 options to test comprehension and prevent cheating by randomizing options. Questions focused on understanding proof techniques and addressing common misconceptions. Various communication platforms like Moodle chat and WhatsApp enabled quick interactions, enhancing student support. Feedback suggested high engagement and slightly improved success rates compared to pre-pandemic settings. However, the reliance on experienced staff for MCQ construction highlighted potential constraints in staff development and module rotation.

Introduction to Numerical Methods

Content Delivery (CK, TK)

This course was offered on two different campuses (learning sites). The lecture and tutorial timetables did not overlap. Lectures were recorded on Zoom by each lecturer and loaded on both course Moodle pages. Additional online videos and notes sourced from the web were added to both Moodle pages (PK and TK). The content uploaded in 2020 was tweaked slightly for 2021 but largely remained the same. This greatly reduced the teaching effort of the lecturers involved.

Lecturers committed to running tutorials "live". Students were encouraged to attend these sessions only if they had questions (due to data-scarcity issues). Unfortunately, this led to minimal attendance at tutorials with 90% of the class not attending. Students were also encouraged to email the lecturer and tutors questions but this invitation was rarely, if ever, taken up.

Assessment and Evaluation (PK and TK)

Students did complain about the time allocation as they felt that more time should have been allocated for the assessments as would be the case for standard in-person testing. It was clear that many students used the full time allocated to work out the solutions and left the uploading to the final few minutes. Due to connectivity issues, a few did not manage to upload their solutions in time. To maintain the integrity of the examining process, no emailed solutions were accepted (as indicated to the students throughout the course).

The overall success-rate was higher in in the pandemic years as opposed to the contact teaching pass-rate pre-pandemic. Interestingly, it seemed as though students were really learning just enough to pass with the majority of marks in the 50-60% range.

7. Final Level Teaching (3rd and 4th year: specialist courses)

In this section we consider courses taught to more mature students at the third or 4th year level of Mathematics. Essentially these are students that are specializing in Mathematics or Applied Mathematics.

Dynamical Systems and Differential Equations (3rd year)

Content Delivery (CK, TK)

This course content featured dynamical systems of the continuous and discrete forms (CK). Video lectures using a tablet PC and the software pdfannotator were prepared. The lectures were given LIVE and recorded using Zoom and uploaded onto the Moodle content management system of the university (PK and TK). This most closely resembled the traditional classroom teaching modality and the only departure this time round was that the lecture was presented over the Zoom platform.

The negative feature of the online mode was clearly the absence of students and their right to ask questions live. The missing normal vibe of a class was clearly palpable. Students had to view the video lectures and had the opportunity to ask the lecturer questions either through the blog on Moodle or through emails. In addition each class had a 150 minute Live session each week where they could meet the lecturer, work on tutorial problems and raise questions during that time. It turned out that very few students availed themselves of this opportunity. A number of students attended the sessions just before assessments as they were examination oriented. The exam-driven learning process is not novel to the pandemic period. It was common during ordinary teaching sessions pre-pandemic. Of course this didactic phenomenon of 'teaching to the test' has been amply discussed in the literature. For example see Phelps [34].

Teaching in the form of Zoom lectures required substantially more effort than standard teaching. One's level of preparedness had to be higher than normal and clinical since the session was being recorded and the lecturer could not risk making mistakes and being corrected by the class. During traditional teaching, occasional errors during

calculations are common and are part of the pedagogical system. It turns out to be a useful way to keep students fully engaged in the lectures. The delivery during the lecture had to be deliberate and extra clear. Preparation and uploading of lectures each day was indeed a time-consuming activity.

Assessment and Evaluation (PK and TK)

Assessments for this course were done through traditional written tests. The questions went live at a certain time and students had to download the one page pdf, work on the problems and at the closing time take photos of their answer pages and upload them onto the Moodle site before the preset closing time arrived. It was pointed out to students that since no active monitoring systems were available, they could make use of class notes, lecture videos, tutorial solutions, youtube videos and Google but were cautioned that this could cost them valuable time. The questions were all novel and at the level of third year it was assumed that outside help would be minimal. Given that calculations could be lengthy it was also assumed that the situation of good students helping poorly prepared students via Whatsapp or other messaging services, would be at a minimum. It was mentioned to the class that on- the-spot self teaching during the test would be time consuming and that they would not complete the assessments in the allotted time.

From the point of view of what type of questions should be examined, it was clear that standard bookwork questions such as stating and proving a theorem would be avoided. Additionally questions had to be novel in the sense that they could not be too closely aligned to examples dealt with in lectures lest students merely copy the method and make appropriate changes. In this regard, generating 'original' questions proved to be another time-consuming challenge. Lecturers knew well that copying and pasting of questions from the web carried the risk that students could find these questions and perhaps their solutions online.

Ordinary Differential Equations (Honours/ 4th year course)

Content Delivery (CK, TK)

The lecturer noted that fortunately, most of this course material was already online, including detailed lecture notes (all using Moodle) for the normal teaching mode. Switching to online only mode, required the upload of audio files covering the notes on a weekly basis (TK). The students were expected to review uploaded material during the normal lecture periods (we ran a formal lecture timetable). There were two sessions of 90 minutes each.

As is common with Honours classes, the number of students enrolled is low and of these only a small number attended the tutorials regularly. A few bright students who engaged with the material did log in to ask questions. They also regularly submitted queries by email. However, the majority of students did not engage at all. The main challenge that students experienced was the perceived workload. As the material was delivered online, it was left to them to listen/watch the material and to complete the tasks set. They largely could not handle this aspect of the experience.

Assessment and Evaluation (PK and TK)

Standard written tests were administered as the form of assessment. It was found that students needed much more time than normal for assessments. Tests that would usually take 60 minutes in person now were allowed 120 minutes. The lecturer's concession to extend the time to 90 minutes was seen to be too little and consequently 120 minutes were utilised.

Tensor Analysis (3rd year)***Content Delivery (CK, TK)***

To maximise the strengths and opportunities and counter the weaknesses and threats, the following steps were adopted during the teaching of the course:

To ensure a level playing field for all students in the class, it was necessary to use internet data-light uploads. To achieve this step by step, well explained lecture notes were developed. The notes and the tutorial questions were uploaded in the usual .pdf format that takes a few kilobytes of data (PK and TK). Additionally audio podcasts were prepared for all lectures. This was not merely a reading out of the notes, but a complete audio enactment of a given class lecture. In other words, the students were guided through the notes in exactly the same way one would in a classroom, with all the stories, anecdotes and jokes to ensure their attention and interest in the topic. The lecturer synthesized his memory of famous FM radio podcasters on how to make the audio podcasts more effective (TK). Any audio podcast for a given lecture was of the order of around 20 megabytes of data. These together with a short zoom discussion session would then be the complete upload for each lecture and this was indeed extremely data-light in the present context.

Assessment and Evaluation (PK and TK)

To overcome the challenge of monitoring against usage of any unfair means during the assessment process, the techniques of open book examinations and take-home examinations were adopted. The questions were framed in such a way that the answers will not readily be available in the books or internet, but students had to use the concepts available there to solve the problems. Composing novel questions posed a clear challenge however the lecturer was satisfied that he had done so effectively.

Although, generally in Mathematics courses it is not customary to use "essay writing" as an assessment method, nevertheless such was implemented in this course. Every student was given a separate topic, from the course material, which ensured that they could not copy from each other. They were instructed to collect information from all possible sources on the internet and books. However it was also instructed that all sources should be duly acknowledged in a compulsory reference section in their essays. Furthermore, the maximum number of mathematical equations that could be used was also restricted, so that they could concentrate on the main concepts, rather than blindly copying some mathematical steps. The students did take this as a challenge and performed extremely well.

As a part of continuous assessment, and to gauge their level of understanding of the topics, numerous short quizzes in multiple choice question format were also provided. Although it is difficult to monitor usage of unfair means in these quizzes, nevertheless these ensured a continuous revision of the topics covered as the course progressed.

8. Impact of online system on pass rates

It is also instructive to analyze the trends in pass-rates amongst the different modules. The historical data obtained from the class records are as in the table below:

Table 1: Pass-rates in each module from 2017 to 2022

Year	1 Management	1 Life Science	1 Engineering	2 Discrete	2 Numerical	3 Dynamical	3 Tensors	4 Differential
2017	85	91	79	82	93	100	95	82
2018	77	93	82	90	91	100	96	75
2019	85	92	80	82	87	79	100	31
2020	91	91	96	95	97	86	100	67
2021	89	96	98	92	95	97	90	71
2022	91	91	97	85	93	91	97	73

Table 2 shows the pass-rate per year in each module as a percentage. That there was a general improvement in the region of approximately 5% may be inferred from a study of the average performance before covid (BC) that is in the years 2017 to 2020 compared to the average pass-rate during 2021 and 22 which were the covid years (CO). Admittedly this would be a crude statistical measure however the trend is clearly evident from the comparison illustrated below:

Figure 1: Comparison of average pass-rates before covid (2017 – 2020) and during covid (2021, 2022)

The plots depicted above in Figure 1 show for each module the BC pass-rate on the left and the CO pass-rate on the right. In all but one case, it may be observed that the CO pass-rate is higher suggesting better academic performance on account of the online teaching and assessment regimes. Only in the case of Tensors was a decline noticeable. This may be traced to the non-standard approach of the assessor in using open-ended questions as opposed to objective type items. The skill levels are evidently higher than when MCQ type items are used and where there is access to other resources such as the internet, books and class notes. Looking ahead, the practicality and value of open-ended questions will undergo closer scrutiny on account of the emergence of generative artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT4.

The plot below (Figure 2), shows the information in Table 2 over the 6 year period for each year and a general improvement can be detected during the covid years.

Figure 2: Individual pass-rates for each module from 2017 to 2022

The case of Ordinary Differential Equations, contains an outlier in 2019 that interferes with the average. Nevertheless an improvement in pass-rates can be observed in the CO periods. The drop in performance in Tensors is also visible in Figure 2. However, in general most modules showed an upward trend during the CO periods 2021 and 2022. We should remark that taking the average pass-rates as an indicator does pose some difficulties. For instance, the cohorts of students are different from year to year. Especially in a low-enrolment course such as Differential Equations do the differences play a major role. On the other hand, the differences are mitigated in modules where there are high enrolments such as at first level.

9. Analysis and the way forward

Online teaching and learning can effectively replace traditional methods, but the necessity for in-person assessments remains critical due to concerns over academic integrity. Online resources do not inherently compromise integrity unless students seek

unauthorized help, akin to open-book exams used in advanced mathematics. The online method suits more mature third and fourth-level students well, who understand exam procedures and are less likely to seek external help, aligning with the content's complexity.

Significant challenges faced by both staff and students during the initial transition to online teaching due to the COVID-19 pandemic are diminishing as both groups adapt. This adaptation aligns with the TPACK framework by Mishra and Koehler [23], which emphasizes the seamless integration of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge. During the pandemic, lecturers utilized digital tools to maintain the integrity of mathematical content, crucial due to its hierarchical nature.

Assessment methods had to evolve; introductory courses used timed online quizzes, while advanced courses maintained traditional methods supported by digital submissions. Critiques of TPACK suggest it lacks specific strategies for integrating technology in mathematics and doesn't adequately consider situational factors, as evidenced during the pandemic. Despite its benefits, TPACK should be viewed as a flexible guide rather than a definitive solution, allowing educators to tailor their approaches to specific needs and technological advancements.

10. Conclusions

The research question we endeavoured to answer is whether pandemic style online teaching and learning could have a permanent place in university mathematics pedagogy. To answer this question we solicited the views of seven mathematicians from diverse mathematical fields working in the University of KwaZulu-Natal. These lecturers considered the mode of instruction and also the assessment procedures that were forced upon the establishment due to the covid-19 pandemic. The overwhelming opinion of contributors was that the online modality of teaching could become a permanent feature of teaching university mathematics at the 3rd and 4th year levels. For less mature students a hybrid programme would be favoured where for entry level students it will be advantageous to revert to the full in-person classroom teaching system.

There are of course a number of limitations to the investigation we have conducted. Firstly, it was challenging to gather empirical evidence in the form of surveys and questionnaires given that a life-threatening pandemic was raging. Additionally, we have selected a cross section of courses to analyse more closely. It would be advantageous to have considered all the different courses on offer as each has its own peculiarities. Sadly this was not practical. There were also differences in opinion amongst lecturers on whether all third and fourth level instruction should permanently be moved to the online space. But in general there was agreement that the advantages outweighed the disadvantages. In future work it will be informative to conduct quantitative experiments to gauge students' perceptions of the online teaching platforms.

Regular direct human contact and persistent encouragement by lecturers is understood to be a major factor contributing towards successful outcomes namely acquiring subject knowledge and strengthening skills. In particular methods of proof are vital in the

formative years of a university student. By the second year, the mode can become hybrid in the sense that most lectures can be given online and uploaded whereas the human-contact sessions will take place during tutorials. In all cases, however, in-person examinations remain the most credible form of assessment and evaluation. Implementing these will have a profound impact on the structure and functioning of the traditional university. The demands on the physical infrastructure will certainly decline and the reach of the university will increase thus enhancing inter-university competition to attract the best students. Whatever the final outcome is, we can conclude for a certainty that the pandemic has forced academics to pursue new lines of thinking in the matter of content delivery as well as assessment and evaluation.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Funding

The authors did not receive support from any organization for the submitted work.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable

Conflict of Interest

The authors below affirm that they have no conflict of interest with the research reported in the article.

11. Bibliography

1. Engelbrecht, J. Borba, M. C., Llinares, S. and Kaiser G (2020) Will 2020 be remembered as the year in which education was changed? ZDM, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-020-01185-3>
2. Martinez, J. (2020). Take this pandemic moment to improve education. EduSource. Retrieved from <https://edsources.org/2020/take-this-pandemic-moment-to-improveeducation/633500>.
3. Lederman, D. (2020)(March 18,. Will shift to remote teaching be boon or bane for inline learning? Inside Higher Ed. Retrieved from <file:///D:/COVID/Most%20teaching%20is%20going%20remote.%20Will%20that%20help%20or%20hurt%20online%20learning.html>.
4. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
5. Piaget, J. (1959). The language and thought of the child (Vol. 5). Psychology Press.
6. Courtney S. A., Miller M. E. S. and Gisondo M. J. The Impact of COVID-19 on Teachers' Integration of Digital Technology Contemporary Educational Technology, 2022, 14(4),

- ep387.
7. Ford, J. Digital technologies: Igniting or hindering curiosity in mathematics? *Australian Primary Mathematics Classroom*, (2018) 23(4), 27-32.
 8. Fishman B. J., Penuel W. R., Hegedus S. and Roschelle J. What Happens When the Research Ends? Factors Related to the Sustainability of a Technology-Infused Mathematics Curriculum *Journal of Computers in Mathematics and Science Teaching* (2011) 30(4), 329-353.
 9. Kaput, J. J. (1992). Technology and mathematics education in D. A. Grouws (Ed.), *Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning*, (pp. 515–556). New York: MacMillan Publishing Company.
 10. Waits, B. K., & Demana F. (2000). Calculators in mathematics teaching and learning: Past, present, and future in M. J. Burke & F. R. Curcio (Eds.), *Learning mathematics for a new century* (pp. 51–66). Reston, VA: National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
 11. Nida, M., Khambaria, M., Su Luanb, W., Fauzi, A. and Ayubb, M. (2010).
 12. Technology in Mathematics Teaching: The Pros and Cons *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* Volume 8, Pages 555-560
 13. NCTM (2021), <https://www.nctm.org/Standards-and-Positions/Position-Statements/Strategic-Use-of-Technology-in-Teaching-and-Learning-Mathematics/>
 14. Gadanidis, G., & Geiger, V. (2010). A social perspective on technology enhanced mathematical learning—from collaboration to performance. *ZDM*, 42(1), 91–104
 15. Kastberg, S., & Leatham, K. (2005). Research on graphing calculators at the secondary level: Implications for mathematics teacher education. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 5(1), 25–37.
 16. Nelson, J., Christopher, A., & Mims, C. (2009). TPACK and web 2.0: Transformation of teaching and learning. *Tech Trends*, 53(5), 80–85.
 17. Pierce, R., & Stacey, K. (2010). Mapping pedagogical opportunities provided by mathematics analysis software. *International Journal of Computers for Mathematical Learning*, 15(1), 1–20.
 18. Roschelle, J., Rafanan, K., Bhanot, R., Estrella, G., Penuel, W. R., Nussbaum, M., & Claro, S. (2009). Scaffolding group explanation and feedback with handheld technology: Impact on students' mathematics learning. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 58, 399–419.
 19. Suh, J., & Moyer, P. S. (2007). Developing students' representational fluency using virtual and physical algebra balances. *Journal of Computers in Mathematics and Science Teaching*, 26(2), 155–173.
 20. Watermeyer, R., Crick, T., Knight, C., & Goodall, J. (2021). COVID-19 and digital disruption in UK universities: Affictions and affordances of emergency online migration. *Higher Education*, 81, 623-641. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-020-00561-y>
 21. Rapanta, C., Botturi, L., Goodyear, P., Guàrdia, L., & Koole, M. (2020). Online university teaching during and after the Covid-19 crisis: Refocusing teacher presence and learning activity. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 2(3), 923–945. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-020-00155-y>
 22. Lee, K., Fanguy, M., Bligh, B. & Lu, X. S. (2022) Adoption of online teaching during the COVID-19 Pandemic: a systematic analysis of changes in university teaching activity, *Educational Review*, 74:3, 460-483, DOI: 10.1080/00131911.2021.1978401.
 23. Radmehr, F & Goodchild S. (2022) Switching to Fully Online Teaching and Learning of Mathematics: The Case of Norwegian Mathematics Lecturers and University Students During the Covid-19 Pandemic, *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*, 8, 581 – 611.
 24. Cabuquin, J. C. (2022) Modular and Online Learning Satisfaction in Mathematics Amid COVID-19: Implications for New Normal Teaching Practices, *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajmri.v1i6.954>.
 25. Mathias, J., Saville C. & Leech, S. (2023) Engaging non-mathematics students in mathematics learning through collaborative teaching, *Teaching Mathematics and its*

- Applications: An International Journal of the IMA, hrad003, <https://doi.org/10.1093/teamat/hrad003>.
26. Yin, L. & Yang, Z. (2022) Research on the Influence of Teaching Methods on Mathematics Academic Achievement of College Students During Online Teaching, ICETC '22: Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers October 2022 Pages 304–310 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3572549.3572598>.
 27. Czerniewicz, L., Trotter, H., & Haupt, G. (2019). Online teaching in response to student protests and campus shutdowns: Academics' perspectives. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 43. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0170-1>.
 28. Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for integrating technology in teachers' knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108 (6), 1017–1054.
 29. Koehler, M. J. , Mishra P. and Cain W. *The Journal of Education* 193, No. 3, What is Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) (2013), pp. 13-19.
 30. Schmid M, Brianza E. and Petko D. Developing a short assessment instrument for Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK.xs) and comparing the factor structure of an integrative and a transformative model *Computers & Education* 157, November 2020, 103967.
 31. Fahadi, M. and Khan M. S. H Technology-enhanced Teaching in Engineering Education: Teachers' Knowledge Construction Using TPACK Framework *International Journal of Instruction* April 2022, 15, No.2 pp. 519 – 542.
 32. Shin, T., Koehler, M., Mishra, P., Schmidt, D., Baran, E. & Thompson, A. (2009). Changing Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) through Course Experiences. In I. Gibson, R. Weber, K. McFerrin, R. Carlsen & D. Willis (Eds.), *Proceedings of SITE 2009--Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 4152-4159). Charleston, SC, USA: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE).
 33. Santos, J. M. and Castro, R. D. R. Technological Pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) in action: Application of learning in the classroom by pre-service teachers (PST) *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 3, Issue 1, 2021, 100110.
 34. Trenholm, S. and Peschke, J. (2020) Teaching undergraduate mathematics fully online: a review from the perspective of communities of practice *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* volume 17, Article number: 37.
 35. M. K. Tallent-Runnels, J. A. Thomas, W. Y. Lan, S. Cooper, T. C. Ahern, S. M. Shaw, and X. Liu (2006) *Teaching Courses Online: A Review of the Research* *Review of Educational Research* 76 (1), 93–135.
 36. L. Mishra, T. Gupta and A. Shree Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic *International Journal of Educational Research Open* 1 (2020) 100012
 37. Tam, G., & El-Azar, D. (2020). 3 ways the coronavirus pandemic could reshape education March 13. *World Economic Forum: Global agenda* Retrieved from file:///D:/COVID/3%20ways%20the%20coronavirus%20pandemic%20could%20reshape%20education%20World%20Economic%20Forum.html.
 38. Zayapragassarazan, Z. (2020). In COVID-19: Strategies for online engagement of remote learners: 9 (pp. 1–11). F1000Research. Org/. 10.7490/f1000research.1117835.1.
 39. Phelps, R. P. (2011). "Teach to the Test?". *The Wilson Quarterly*. 35 (4): 38–42.
 40. Comas-Forgas, R., Lancaster, T., Calvo-Sastre, A., & Sureda-Negre, J. (2021). Exam cheating and academic integrity breaches during the COVID-19 pandemic: An analysis of internet search activity in Spain. *Heliyon*, 7(10), e08233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08233>
 - Roschelle, J., Shechtman, N., Tatar, D., Hegedus, S., Hopkins, B., Empson, S., Knudsen, J., & Gallagher, L. (2010). Integration of technology, curriculum, and professional development for advancing middle school mathematics: Three large-scale studies.

American Educational Research Journal, 47(4), 833–878.

41. Johnson, A. M., Jacovina, M. E., Russell, D. E., & Soto, C. M. (2016). Challenges and solutions when using technologies in the classroom. In S. A. Crossley & D. S. McNamara (Eds.) Adaptive educational technologies for literacy instruction (pp. 13-29). New York: Taylor & Francis